

1 **NLRP7 regulates the lin28 pathway.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

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8 NLR family control of developmental transitions and of protein/RNA complexes with embryonic functions is
9 not widely understood. We describe here control of lin28 by NLRP7.

10 Citations

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